

Report on the second Needs analysis

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Needs analysis purpose

Need analysis represents the part of the researchers' activities that follow the return phase, together with Focus group and Delphi study. Precisely, after each secondment to non-academic partner, upon returning to their home country, talents present the key issues and ideas from secondment phase and, together with researchers identify the situation and assess the needs of the business community in each widening country.

The second part of Needs analysis is aimed at getting information about sustainability business practice and sustainability reporting limitations and opportunities, from the business community point of view. It is based on the questionnaire, which was produced as the result of the Delphi study. During period February - March, questionnaire was formulated and then used for collecting data. Data were collected in all four widening countries: Serbia, Albania, Bosnia & Herzegovina, North Macedonia.

Needs analysis should show what aspects of sustainability and which sustainability practices, previously identified and confirmed by experts, are considered as the most important by overall business community, regardless the industry type or size. The idea is to use the analysis results to decide which sustainability aspects are the least developed and which sustainability practices are the most needed by the business community so have to be included into the training programme that will be composed under each center for entrepreneurship and innovation (EI centers).

Research results – sample structure

Research refers to the sample of 100 companies, whereby 25 questionnaires were collected in each widening country. The following tables describe the sample.

Table 1. Number of companies by countries

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Albania	25	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Bosnia and Herzegovina	25	25.0	25.0	50.0
	North Macedonia	25	25.0	25.0	75.0
	Serbia	25	25.0	25.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

From the total number of companies in the sample, the majority refers to small companies (43), then medium (32) and large (25).

Funded by
the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Table 2. Company size

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Large	25	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Medium	32	32.0	32.0	57.0
	Small	43	43.0	43.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Taking into account the companies' activities, the largest participation in the sample have companies from the fields of Financial and insurance activities (13%), Manufacturing industry (12%), Information and Communications (10%) and Education (10%).

Table 3. Company's activity

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Area A	4	4.0	4.0	4.0
Area C	12	12.0	12.0	16.0
Area D	1	1.0	1.0	17.0
Area E	2	2.0	2.0	19.0
Area F	9	9.0	9.0	28.0
Area G	8	8.0	8.0	36.0
Area H	1	1.0	1.0	37.0
Area I	1	1.0	1.0	38.0
Area J	10	10.0	10.0	48.0
Area K	13	13.0	13.0	61.0
Area L	5	5.0	5.0	66.0
Area M	7	7.0	7.0	73.0
Area N	3	3.0	3.0	76.0
Area O	1	1.0	1.0	77.0
Area P	10	10.0	10.0	87.0
Area Q	3	3.0	3.0	90.0
Area S	9	9.0	9.0	99.0
Area U	1	1.0	1.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Considering the gender, the largest number of companies is managed by men, in 54% of cases.

Funded by
the European Union

Table 4. Gender structure of managers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	46	46.0	46.0	46.0
	Male	54	54.0	54.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

The largest percentage of managers have Higher professional education (89%) and Higher vocational education (9%). Only 2% of managers in the sample have Secondary education.

Table 5. Manager’s education

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Higher professional education	89	89.0	89.0	89.0
	Higher vocational education	9	9.0	9.0	98.0
	Secondary education	2	2.0	2.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Research results – statistical analysis

According to the research results and descriptive statistical analysis, all tested variables were rated very high (Table 6). The average ratings of all is higher than 4, except those two: “To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems]” (3.72) and “To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan]” (3.88). The highest average ratings are achieved for the following variables: To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d] Work conditions and health at work] (4.59), To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d] Waste management] (4.59) and To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [c] Pollution control] (4.58). Also, the standard deviation shows a high degree of agreement between the managers on the ratings of the tested variables. In this regard, the conclusion is that all variables are extremely important, as well as that the right variables were selected during the design of the survey questionnaire.

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Table 6. Descriptive statistics of tested variables

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [a] Energy management]	100	4.48	.785
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [b] Energy efficiency]	100	4.54	.744
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [c] Pollution control]	100	4.58	.771
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d] Waste management]	100	4.59	.780
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [e] Protection of biodiversity]	100	4.45	.783
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [a] Training for the education of workers]	100	4.39	.737
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [b] Cooperation with stakeholders]	100	4.32	.634
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [c] Transparency in reporting]	100	4.28	.854
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [d] Economic growth]	100	4.47	.731
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [e] Socially responsible business practices]	100	4.43	.714
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [a] Employee training]	100	4.40	.725
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [b] Increasing awareness of waste classification]	100	4.30	.798
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [c] Social inclusion]	100	4.22	.799
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d] Work conditions and health at work]	100	4.59	.683
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [e] Community engagement]	100	4.32	.695
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [a] Investment in human resources]	100	4.40	.778
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [b] Transparency of business]	100	4.24	.933
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [c] Lack of resources]	100	4.23	.941
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [d] Legislation]	100	4.46	.797

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [e] Low level of public awareness]	100	4.33	.933
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [a] Social benefits]	100	4.12	.891
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [b] Infrastructure development]	100	4.38	.776
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [c] Cooperation with the community]	100	4.25	.716
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [d] Resource optimization]	100	4.43	.807
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [e] Cost reduction]	100	4.30	.927
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [a] Energy efficiency]	100	4.22	.917
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems]	100	3.72	1.064
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment]	100	4.03	1.020
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [d] Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders]	100	4.16	.929
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [e] Promotion and education]	100	4.37	.849
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [a] Strategies]	100	4.19	.940
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan]	100	3.88	1.094
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [c] Partnerships and networks]	100	4.23	.962
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [d] Financial motivation]	100	4.33	.888
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e] Satisfied employees]	100	4.46	.861
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [a] Transparency in work]	100	4.20	.791
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [b] Education of employees]	100	4.27	.851
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [c] Digitalization and data sharing]	100	4.44	.686
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [d] Communication efficiency]	100	4.41	.698

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [e) Sharing information]	100	4.50	.674
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [a) Better management of all types of waste]	100	4.33	.821
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [b) Digitalization of processes in all sectors]	100	4.30	.810
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [c) Innovative solutions for water resource management]	100	4.11	.973
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [d) Promotion of production with less waste]		4.26	.981
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [e) Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens]		4.27	.952
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [a) Stakeholder engagement and trust building]		4.25	.809
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [b) Learning and improvement]		4.43	.671
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [c) Increasing competitiveness]		4.38	.678
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [d) Access to credit lines]		4.05	.845
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [e) Long term value creation]		4.44	.820
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [a) Lack of reporting knowledge]		4.10	.847
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [b) Lack of support programs]		4.18	.857
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [c) Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations]		4.21	.782
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d) Lack of standardization]		4.22	.773
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [e) Complexity and reporting burden]		4.08	.849
Valid N (listwise)			

Taking into account the size of the company and the average ratings of the analysed variables, it is concluded that all variables are very important regardless of the size of the company since average ratings in most cases are greater than 4 (Table 7). The following variables got the lowest ratings: How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a) Interviewing] (3.91 and

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

only in the case of medium companies); To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems] (3.76 for large, 3.72 for medium and 3.70 for small companies); To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan] (3.76 for large and 3.88 for small companies) and To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [a] Social benefits] (3.97 for medium companies). The biggest discrepancy in ratings between different size companies was found for variable: To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [a] Energy management]; To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [e] Community engagement]; To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [a] Transparency in work]; To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Lack of standardization].

Table 7. Average ratings by company size

Size	Large		Medium		Small		Total	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [a] Energy management]	4.64	.569	4.41	.979	4.44	.734	4.48	.785
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [b] Energy efficiency]	4.72	.542	4.38	.942	4.56	.666	4.54	.744
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [c] Pollution control]	4.68	.690	4.23	1.023	4.77	.480	4.58	.771
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d] Waste management]	4.56	.712	4.41	1.073	4.74	.492	4.59	.780
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [e] Protection of biodiversity]	4.52	.714	4.38	.907	4.47	.735	4.45	.783
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects	4.36	.638	4.34	.937	4.44	.629	4.39	.737

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

of sustainability? [a] Training for the education of workers]								
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [b] Cooperation with stakeholders]	4.28	.614	4.28	.772	4.37	.536	4.32	.634
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [c] Transparency in reporting]	4.36	.757	4.16	1.081	4.33	.715	4.28	.854
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [d] Economic growth]	4.40	.707	4.50	.916	4.49	.592	4.47	.731
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [e] Socially responsible business practices]	4.48	.653	4.31	.931	4.49	.551	4.43	.714
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [a] Employee training]	4.52	.586	4.38	.942	4.35	.613	4.40	.725
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [b] Increasing awareness of waste classification]	4.44	.821	4.09	.856	4.37	.725	4.30	.798
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [c] Social inclusion]	4.40	.707	4.09	1.027	4.21	.638	4.22	.799
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d] Work conditions and health at work]	4.72	.542	4.47	.950	4.60	.495	4.59	.683
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [e] Community engagement]	4.48	.653	4.25	.842	4.28	.591	4.32	.695
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [a] Investment in human resources]	4.56	.583	4.31	.965	4.37	.725	4.40	.778

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [b] Transparency of business]	4.28	.891	4.00	1.244	4.40	.623	4.24	.933
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [c] Lack of resources]	4.24	.970	3.91	1.146	4.47	.667	4.23	.941
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [d] Legislation]	4.40	.707	4.34	1.066	4.58	.587	4.46	.797
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [e] Low level of public awareness]	4.16	1.106	4.25	1.107	4.49	.631	4.33	.933
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [a] Social benefits]	4.40	.707	3.97	1.031	4.07	.856	4.12	.891
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [b] Infrastructure development]	4.48	.653	4.31	1.061	4.37	.578	4.38	.776
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [c] Cooperation with the community]	4.36	.700	4.16	.884	4.26	.581	4.25	.716
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [d] Resource optimization]	4.64	.569	4.25	1.047	4.44	.700	4.43	.807
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [e] Cost reduction]	4.40	1.080	4.28	1.054	4.26	.727	4.30	.927

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [a] Energy efficiency]	4.28	.936	4.19	1.030	4.21	.833	4.22	.917
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems]	3.76	1.012	3.72	1.114	3.70	1.081	3.72	1.064
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment]	4.08	1.077	3.91	1.118	4.09	.921	4.03	1.020
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [d] Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders]	4.40	.816	3.84	1.194	4.26	.693	4.16	.929
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [e] Promotion and education]	4.36	.860	4.31	.998	4.42	.731	4.37	.849
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [a] Strategies]	4.12	1.130	4.25	.916	4.19	.852	4.19	.940
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan]	3.76	1.165	4.06	1.014	3.81	1.118	3.88	1.094
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [c] Partnerships and networks]	4.20	1.041	4.09	1.088	4.35	.813	4.23	.962
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [d] Financial motivation]	4.28	1.061	4.19	.965	4.47	.702	4.33	.888

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e] Satisfied employees]	4.36	.860	4.35	1.050	4.60	.695	4.46	.861
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [a] Transparency in work]	4.44	.821	4.16	.847	4.09	.718	4.20	.791
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [b] Education of employees]	4.36	.952	4.25	.916	4.23	.751	4.27	.851
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [c] Digitalization and data sharing]	4.56	.583	4.38	.793	4.42	.663	4.44	.686
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [d] Communication efficiency]	4.56	.651	4.38	.833	4.35	.613	4.41	.698
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [e] Sharing information]	4.72	.458	4.41	.911	4.44	.548	4.50	.674
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [a] Better management of all types of waste]	4.48	.653	4.13	.922	4.40	.821	4.33	.821
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [b] Digitalization of processes in all sectors]	4.64	.569	4.13	.942	4.23	.782	4.30	.810
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [c] Innovative solutions for water resource management]	4.28	.737	4.00	1.218	4.09	.895	4.11	.973
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [d] Promotion of production with less waste]	4.20	1.000	4.19	1.091	4.35	.897	4.26	.981

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [e] Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens]	4.40	.707	4.16	1.139	4.28	.934	4.27	.952
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [a] Stakeholder engagement and trust building]	4.48	.586	4.06	1.014	4.26	.727	4.25	.809
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [b] Learning and improvement]	4.56	.507	4.28	.851	4.47	.592	4.43	.671
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [c] Increasing competitiveness]	4.32	.748	4.34	.745	4.44	.590	4.38	.678
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Access to credit lines]	4.00	.957	3.94	.878	4.16	.754	4.05	.845
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [e] Long term value creation]	4.48	.918	4.38	.976	4.47	.631	4.44	.820
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [a] Lack of reporting knowledge]	4.36	.860	3.94	.914	4.07	.768	4.10	.847
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [b] Lack of support programs]	4.28	.891	4.22	.906	4.09	.811	4.18	.857
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [c] Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations]	4.28	.678	4.09	.856	4.26	.790	4.21	.782

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Lack of standardization]	4.48	.586	4.16	.847	4.12	.793	4.22	.773
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [e] Complexity and reporting burden]	4.24	.926	4.00	.916	4.05	.754	4.08	.849

As well previous results and the analysis of the average ratings of the variables achieved by country, shows enviable results, since in most cases in the analyzed countries the average ratings are above 4. The differences by the countries are analysed and presented in Table 8.

The lowest rated variables in Albania are: To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [b] Education of employees] (3.76); To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Access to credit lines] (3.80); To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment] (3.80); and To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [e] Low level of public awareness] (3.84). Managers in Bosnia and Herzegovina the lowest mark gave to To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems] (3.88); To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment] (3.88) and To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan] (3.88), while the lowest marks in North Macedonia are for variable To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems] (3.76) and To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan] (3.92). In Serbia, the lowest marks were given to variables To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems] (3.72) and To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan] (3.88).

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Table 8. Average ratings by country

Country	Albania		B&H		North Mcd		Serbia		Total	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [a] Energy management]	4.20	1.080	4.64	.569	4.64	.490	4.44	.821	4.48	.785
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [b] Energy efficiency]	4.32	.988	4.56	.583	4.80	.408	4.48	.823	4.54	.744
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [c] Pollution control]	4.42	.974	4.56	.651	4.72	.614	4.60	.816	4.58	.771
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d] Waste management]	4.32	1.145	4.72	.458	4.76	.523	4.56	.768	4.59	.780
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [e] Protection of biodiversity]	4.32	.852	4.44	.821	4.56	.712	4.48	.770	4.45	.783
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [a] Training for the education of workers]	3.92	.997	4.52	.510	4.56	.583	4.56	.583	4.39	.737
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [b] Cooperation with stakeholders]	4.16	.688	4.32	.690	4.32	.557	4.48	.586	4.32	.634
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [c] Transparency in reporting]	3.96	.978	4.16	.898	4.52	.714	4.48	.714	4.28	.854

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [d] Economic growth]	4.16	1.028	4.60	.500	4.52	.586	4.60	.645	4.47	.731
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [e] Socially responsible business practices]	4.32	.852	4.40	.707	4.48	.653	4.52	.653	4.43	.714
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [a] Employee training]	3.96	.889	4.40	.645	4.72	.458	4.52	.653	4.40	.725
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [b] Increasing awareness of waste classification]	4.04	.790	4.24	.879	4.52	.653	4.40	.816	4.30	.798
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [c] Social inclusion]	3.88	.971	4.28	.792	4.36	.638	4.36	.700	4.22	.799
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d] Work conditions and health at work]	4.24	1.012	4.68	.476	4.68	.557	4.76	.436	4.59	.683
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [e] Community engagement]	4.16	.800	4.28	.614	4.40	.645	4.44	.712	4.32	.695
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [a] Investment in human resources]	4.20	1.000	4.40	.764	4.60	.577	4.40	.707	4.40	.778
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable	4.20	1.118	4.20	.764	4.44	.768	4.12	1.054	4.24	.933

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

practices in your country? [b] Transparency of business]										
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [c] Lack of resources]	3.88	1.130	4.32	.690	4.52	.823	4.20	1.000	4.23	.941
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [d] Legislation]	3.96	1.172	4.64	.490	4.68	.557	4.56	.583	4.46	.797
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [e] Low level of public awareness]	3.84	1.248	4.40	.764	4.64	.638	4.44	.821	4.33	.933
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [a] Social benefits]	4.08	1.077	4.04	.889	4.28	.737	4.08	.862	4.12	.891
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [b] Infrastructure development]	4.24	1.052	4.52	.586	4.36	.700	4.40	.707	4.38	.776
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [c] Cooperation with the community]	4.16	.898	4.20	.645	4.28	.678	4.36	.638	4.25	.716
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [d] Resource optimization]	4.20	.913	4.28	.843	4.60	.645	4.64	.757	4.43	.807
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing	4.20	1.080	4.28	.843	4.16	1.106	4.56	.583	4.30	.927

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

sustainable practices? [e] Cost reduction]										
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [a] Energy efficiency]	4.00	1.041	4.16	.850	4.44	.821	4.28	.936	4.22	.917
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems]	3.64	1.075	3.88	.971	3.76	1.128	3.60	1.118	3.72	1.064
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment]	3.80	.957	3.88	.881	4.28	1.208	4.16	.987	4.03	1.020
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [d] Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders]	3.88	1.201	3.96	.790	4.52	.714	4.28	.843	4.16	.929
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [e] Promotion and education]	4.16	1.028	4.36	.860	4.60	.707	4.36	.757	4.37	.849
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [a] Strategies]	3.88	1.013	4.24	.879	4.48	.918	4.16	.898	4.19	.940
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan]	3.84	1.106	3.88	1.013	3.92	1.222	3.88	1.092	3.88	1.094

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [c] Partnerships and networks]	4.00	1.080	4.16	.943	4.44	.917	4.32	.900	4.23	.962
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [d] Financial motivation]	4.00	1.118	4.28	.678	4.44	.917	4.60	.707	4.33	.888
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e] Satisfied employees]	4.04	1.160	4.48	.770	4.88	.332	4.44	.821	4.46	.861
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [a] Transparency in work]	3.96	.841	4.20	.816	4.44	.712	4.20	.764	4.20	.791
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [b] Education of employees]	3.76	1.052	4.48	.586	4.44	.712	4.40	.816	4.27	.851
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [c] Digitalization and data sharing]	4.28	.792	4.28	.737	4.56	.583	4.64	.569	4.44	.686
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [d] Communication efficiency]	4.16	.800	4.40	.707	4.44	.651	4.64	.569	4.41	.698
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [e] Sharing information]	4.24	.926	4.44	.583	4.64	.490	4.68	.557	4.50	.674
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [a] Better	4.29	.806	4.32	.748	4.28	.936	4.44	.821	4.33	.821

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

management of all types of waste]										
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [b] Digitalization of processes in all sectors]	4.08	.862	4.24	.879	4.56	.712	4.32	.748	4.30	.810
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [c] Innovative solutions for water resource management]	3.92	.997	4.28	.936	4.08	1.038	4.16	.943	4.11	.973
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [d] Promotion of production with less waste]	4.16	.987	4.32	.900	4.24	1.165	4.32	.900	4.26	.981
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [e] Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens]	4.08	1.077	4.32	1.069	4.28	.980	4.40	.645	4.27	.952
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [a] Stakeholder engagement and trust building]	4.04	1.060	4.12	.726	4.44	.768	4.40	.577	4.25	.809
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [b] Learning and improvement]	4.24	.779	4.44	.651	4.60	.500	4.44	.712	4.43	.671

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [c] Increasing competitiveness]	4.32	.852	4.24	.597	4.52	.653	4.44	.583	4.38	.678
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Access to credit lines]	3.80	.913	4.00	.707	4.12	1.013	4.28	.678	4.05	.845
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [e] Long term value creation]	4.24	.926	4.44	.768	4.64	.907	4.44	.651	4.44	.820
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [a] Lack of reporting knowledge]	4.08	.702	4.04	.978	4.16	.800	4.12	.927	4.10	.847
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [b] Lack of support programs]	4.12	.781	4.24	.779	4.20	.913	4.16	.987	4.18	.857
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [c] Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations]	4.04	.841	4.28	.737	4.08	.862	4.44	.651	4.21	.782
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d] Lack of standardization]	4.36	.757	4.04	.935	4.32	.748	4.16	.624	4.22	.773
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [e] Complexity and reporting burden]	4.16	.850	4.08	.909	4.08	.812	4.00	.866	4.08	.849

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

Regardless of gender, all variables were rated highly, with scores higher than 4, except in the case of the following options: How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [a] Interviewing] (average rating 3.97 from the woman's point of view) and How important is each of the following ways to assess/recognize the soft skills of individuals? [c] Reference checks] (average ratings according to both men and women are lower than 4, or 3.69 and 3.73 respectively). The analysis of the results based on the managers' gender is presented in Table 9.

Table 9. Average ratings according to gender of the managers

Gender	Female		Male		Total	
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [a] Energy management]	4.61	.577	4.37	.917	4.48	.785
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [b] Energy efficiency]	4.63	.610	4.46	.840	4.54	.744
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [c] Pollution control]	4.76	.565	4.42	.887	4.58	.771
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d] Waste management]	4.74	.575	4.46	.905	4.59	.780
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [e] Protection of biodiversity]	4.61	.577	4.31	.907	4.45	.783
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [a] Training for the education of workers]	4.54	.690	4.26	.757	4.39	.737
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [b] Cooperation with stakeholders]	4.48	.505	4.19	.702	4.32	.634
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [c] Transparency in reporting]	4.50	.691	4.09	.937	4.28	.854
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [d] Economic growth]	4.50	.753	4.44	.718	4.47	.731
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [e] Socially responsible business practices]	4.59	.617	4.30	.768	4.43	.714
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [a] Employee training]	4.50	.691	4.31	.748	4.40	.725

Funded by the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [b] Increasing awareness of waste classification]	4.41	.748	4.20	.833	4.30	.798
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [c] Social inclusion]	4.22	.786	4.22	.816	4.22	.799
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d] Work conditions and health at work]	4.63	.679	4.56	.691	4.59	.683
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [e] Community engagement]	4.39	.614	4.26	.757	4.32	.695
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [a] Investment in human resources]	4.50	.587	4.31	.907	4.40	.778
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [b] Transparency of business]	4.24	.899	4.24	.970	4.24	.933
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [c] Lack of resources]	4.22	.964	4.24	.930	4.23	.941
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [d] Legislation]	4.50	.810	4.43	.792	4.46	.797
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [e] Low level of public awareness]	4.35	.948	4.31	.928	4.33	.933
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [a] Social benefits]	4.24	.822	4.02	.942	4.12	.891
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [b] Infrastructure development]	4.54	.622	4.24	.867	4.38	.776
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [c] Cooperation with the community]	4.46	.622	4.07	.749	4.25	.716
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [d] Resource optimization]	4.63	.532	4.26	.955	4.43	.807
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [e] Cost reduction]	4.48	.809	4.15	.998	4.30	.927

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [a] Energy efficiency]	4.30	.840	4.15	.979	4.22	.917
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [b] Water management systems]	3.78	1.009	3.67	1.116	3.72	1.064
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [c] Promotion of sustainable investment]	4.15	.942	3.93	1.079	4.03	1.020
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [d] Transparency, communication and reporting to stakeholders]	4.30	.756	4.04	1.045	4.16	.929
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [e] Promotion and education]	4.46	.780	4.30	.903	4.37	.849
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [a] Strategies]	4.30	.891	4.09	.976	4.19	.940
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [b] Waste management plan]	4.00	1.033	3.78	1.144	3.88	1.094
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [c] Partnerships and networks]	4.39	.829	4.09	1.051	4.23	.962
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [d] Financial motivation]	4.39	.856	4.28	.920	4.33	.888
To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e] Satisfied employees]	4.37	.878	4.55	.845	4.46	.861
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [a] Transparency in work]	4.37	.711	4.06	.834	4.20	.791
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [b] Education of employees]	4.39	.829	4.17	.863	4.27	.851
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [c] Digitalization and data sharing]	4.50	.658	4.39	.712	4.44	.686
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [d] Communication efficiency]	4.48	.623	4.35	.756	4.41	.698
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [e] Sharing information]	4.59	.541	4.43	.767	4.50	.674

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [a) Better management of all types of waste]	4.54	.721	4.15	.864	4.33	.821
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [b) Digitalization of processes in all sectors]	4.39	.745	4.22	.861	4.30	.810
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [c) Innovative solutions for water resource management]	4.22	.917	4.02	1.019	4.11	.973
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [d) Promotion of production with less waste]	4.41	.884	4.13	1.047	4.26	.981
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [e) Collaboration among government institutions, businesses, professionals and citizens]	4.46	.808	4.11	1.040	4.27	.952
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [a) Stakeholder engagement and trust building]	4.39	.649	4.13	.912	4.25	.809
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [b) Learning and improvement]	4.54	.622	4.33	.700	4.43	.671
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [c) Increasing competitiveness]	4.39	.614	4.37	.734	4.38	.678
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [d) Access to credit lines]	4.07	.742	4.04	.931	4.05	.845
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [e) Long term value creation]	4.54	.585	4.35	.974	4.44	.820
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [a) Lack of reporting knowledge]	4.15	.816	4.06	.878	4.10	.847
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [b) Lack of support programs]	4.17	.877	4.19	.848	4.18	.857
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [c) Lack of prescribed legal and other regulations]	4.24	.794	4.19	.779	4.21	.782
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d) Lack of standardization]	4.24	.705	4.20	.833	4.22	.773

**Funded by
the European Union**

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [e) Complexity and reporting burden]	4.09	.839	4.07	.866	4.08	.849
---	------	------	------	------	------	------

For a smaller number of variables, the average ratings given by women and men are completely the same. Only the following 3 variables received higher average ratings from men compared to women: To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [c) Lack of resources]; To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e) Satisfied employees] and To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [b) Lack of support programs]. For all other variables, average ratings from men are lower in comparison to the average ratings for woman. It may be explained as higher awareness of women towards sustainability practice and sustainability issues in comparison to the men.

Conclusion

The following table points the options with the highest rank under each question. Based on descriptive statistical analysis, it can be concluded that **Waste management** is considered as the most significant ecological aspect of sustainability. When it comes to the economic and social aspects of sustainability, it can be concluded that the most important are **economic growth and work conditions and health at work**, respectively. The most challenging aspect of sustainability practices implementation is **legislation** and the greatest benefit represents **resource optimization**. As the most important sustainable practice is declared **promotion and education**, and the most important driver of sustainability activities in the companies **satisfied employees**. IT support is especially important for **sharing information**. **Long term value creation** is the main opportunity, while **lack of standardization** is the main limitation associated with sustainability reporting. Finally, as the most important circular economy activity is declared **better management of all types of waste**.

Table 10. Sustainability aspects with highest average scores

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
To what extent are significant the following ecological (environmental) aspects of sustainability? [d) Waste management]	100	4.59	.780
To what extent are significant the following economic aspects of sustainability? [d) Economic growth]	100	4.47	.731
To what extent are significant the following social (societal) aspects of sustainability? [d) Work conditions and health at work]	100	4.59	.683
To what extent are significant the following challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in your country? [d) Legislation]	100	4.46	.797
To what extent are significant the following benefits of implementing sustainable practices? [d) Resource optimization]	100	4.43	.807
To what extent are significant the following sustainable practices implemented in your company / country? [e) Promotion and education]	100	4.37	.849

Funded by
the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

To what extent are significant the following drivers of sustainability activities in your company/country? [e) Satisfied employees]	100	4.46	.861
To what extent is significant IT support for the following sustainability aspects? [e) Sharing information]	100	4.50	.674
To what extent are significant the following circular economy activities which can be applied in your country? [a) Better management of all types of waste]	100	4.33	.821
To what extent are significant the following opportunities associated with sustainability reporting? [e) Long term value creation]	100	4.44	.820
To what extent are significant the following limitations associated with sustainability reporting? [d) Lack of standardization]	100	4.22	.773

Due to the average marks, it can be concluded that business representatives that participated quantitative research gave the advantage to the environmental aspects of sustainability, in comparison to the economic and social aspects of sustainability. As specifically important, the following three environmental aspects of sustainability stand out: waste management, pollution control and energy efficiency. Among the challenges/difficulties in implementing sustainable practices in the observed widening countries, it can be concluded that the most challenging once are Investment in human resources and legislation. As the most significant benefits of implementing sustainable practices there are resource optimization and cost reduction, meaning that even not stated exactly still environmental concern under the sustainability concept is led by economic effects. When it comes to the implementation of the sustainable practices in the observed widening countries, the average marks are lower in comparison to their significance. As the most present sustainable practices implemented are promotion and education and energy efficiency.

The role of IT support is seen mostly in terms of sharing information and communication efficiency. The main role of circular economy is connected to the better management of all types of waste. As the most important opportunities associated with sustainability reporting there are learning and improvement and increasing competitiveness. On the other hand, as the most important limitations associated with sustainability reporting there are lack of prescribed legal and other regulations and lack of standardization.

Based on the results of the all four activities (Systematic literature review, Focus groups, Delphi study and Needs analysis) it can be concluded that at least two or three training programmes should be focused on developing **sustainability practices, sustainability reporting, sustainable entrepreneurship, circular economy, environment protection skills.**

The secondments to non-academic partner OCom, from Italy, highlighted the most important aspects and challenges concerning sustainability and sustainability reporting. The widening countries' subsequent situational analysis and needs assessment provided knowledge on specific contexts which R&I capacity should improve. Based on both types of activities, during the secondments and during the return phase, training programmes tailored to the specific business communities' needs and environment will be

Funded by
the European Union

USE IPM

Up-skilling researchers for Sustainable Entrepreneurship based on Innovation Process Management

created by each sending institution in the widening country. Specificities of each widening country, participating in the USE IPM project, will be considered when creating training programmes in at each academic institution, for each EI centre.

**Funded by
the European Union**